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IMPROVING THE RESULTS OF ANESTHESIA IN THYROID PATHOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

The article presents the results of preoperative preparation, anesthesia and surgical treatment of patients operated on for non-toxic nodular goiter. A new approach to preoperative preparation for thyroid surgery is described. The effectiveness in the preoperative period of using the modified method of preoperative preparation using sibazon and droperidol and anesthesia with the use of ketamine and the advantages of this method compared with other methods of general anesthesia are shown.

Keywords: modified preoperative preparation, anesthesia, thyroid gland, nontoxic nodular goiter.

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УЛУЧШЕНИЕ РЕЗУЛЬТАТОВ АНЕСТЕЗИИ ПРИ ПАТОЛОГИИ ЩИТОВИДНОЙ ЖЕЛЕЗЫ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье представлены результаты предоперационной подготовки, анестезии и хирургического лечения больных, оперированных по поводу зоба. Описывается новый подход к предоперационной подготовке. Показана эффективность в предоперационном периоде применения стресс-протекторной подготовки с использованием сибазона и дроперидола и анестезиологического пособия с использованием кетамина и преимущества данного метода по сравнению со другими методами общей анестезии.

Ключевые слова: предоперационная подготовка, анестезия, щитовидная железа, нетоксический зоб.

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КАЛОНСИМОН БЕЗ ПАТОЛОГИЯЛАРИДА АНЕСТЕЗИЯ НАТИЖАЛАРИНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Мақолада қалонсимон без патологияси: нотоксик бўқоқ билан беморларни хирургик давоаланиш давомида операция олди тайёргарлиги, анестезияси натижалари кўрсатилган. Операцияга тайёрлашнинг янги усули тасвирланган. Операция олди тайёргарликка стресс-протектор сифатида сибасон ва дроперидолнинг ишлатилиши самарадорлиги ва анестезия давомида кетаминнинг биргаликда ишлатилиши бошқа усулларда устунлиги ёритилган.

Калит сўзлар: Операция олди тайёргарлиги, анестезия, қалонсимон без, нотоксик бўқоқ,

Introduction:

Thyroid disease is one of the most common diseases, with overt and latent forms occurring in 20 to 50 cases per 10,000 population [4-1]. It disrupts the functioning of almost all organs and organ systems [5], and the most significant changes occur in the circulatory system [6-9]. The main mechanisms of pathological changes in the cardiovascular system in toxic and nontoxic bulls are: first, activation of the sympathetic nervous system, which increases the number of adrenergic receptors in the myocardium and increases its sensitivity to adrenergic substances; second, the direct effect of thyroid hormones on the myocardium [2, 8, 10]. Toxic and nontoxic bulls undergo abrupt changes in hemodynamics: increased heart rate, dilation of blood vessels and the dynamic volume of blood flow, increased heart rate, decreased total peripheral vascular resistance, changes in blood pressure [2, 11, 12], as well as The degree of cardiovascular disorders is directly related to the severity of the toxic and nontoxic bull [13]. Diffuse toxic and nontoxic bovine not only worsens the quality of life of patients, but also significantly increases the risk of surgery, which serves as a basis for contraindications to planned surgery [3, 14] and mandatory preoperative preparation.

The main tasks of preoperative preparation are to eliminate or minimize existing and potential cases of thyrotoxicosis, to restore metabolic processes and to increase the functional capacity of organs and systems that experience maximum stress during and after surgery [8, 14-16].

Methods:

In view of these functions, patients with symptoms of thyrotoxicosis are prescribed preoperative conservative therapy with thyrostatics, glucocorticoids and β -blockers. These groups have both advantages and disadvantages of drug use. Thyrostatics impair the synthesis of thyroid hormones, block the iodine supply of thyroglobulin, and stop the thyroid gland from absorbing iodine [2,17]. However, long-term use of thyrostatics increases the size of the thyroid gland, relaxes the consistency of the thyroid gland, increases blood supply, which worsens the conditions of the operation. To reduce the level of thyroid hormones in the blood, treatment with corticosteroids monotherapy or antithyroid drugs is prescribed, the therapeutic effect is associated with the control of secretory processes and the conversion of peripheral conversion of thyroxine to more active T3. β -blockers are commonly used to compensate for hemodynamic changes with drugs. These drugs do not affect the synthesis and secretion of thyroid hormones, but they do so by blocking the effects of the sympathetic nervous system on the cardiovascular system, leading to a decrease in myocardial contractility and a decrease in its need for oxygen [2]. The use of β -blockers has a positive effect on the function of the sinus node and the conduction system in general. These drugs have been shown to be very effective in the treatment of cardiac arrhythmias such as sinus tachycardia [18, 19], supraventricular forms of extrasystolic arrhythmia [20, 21], and fibrillation [22, 23]. Thus, β -blockers can be used as an element of preoperative preparation, but it should be borne in mind that long-term use of β -blockers without thyrostatic drugs does not have a positive effect, but only eliminates some of the symptoms. [24]. In addition, the appointment of α -blockers with negative inotropic effects in the background of metabolic diseases of the myocardium, specific to patients with toxic and nontoxic goiter, may increase the risk of severe hemodynamic complications (bradycardia, arterial hypotension, systemic perfusion) during surgery. [15].

Results:

Thus, there are certain limitations for each drug or combination of thyrotoxicosis used to reduce preoperative thyrotoxicosis, which reduces the effectiveness of preoperative preparation and does not allow symptomatic compensation in some patients [2,3]. In this context, the main condition for improving the safety of the forthcoming operation is to improve the quality of scheduled premedication and use the modern capabilities of the anesthetic manuals used.

When choosing a means of premedication, it should be borne in mind that patients with toxic and nontoxic hemorrhoids are more likely than other patients to have serious hemodynamics, such as psychoemotional stress associated with delivery to the operating room and waiting for surgery, tachycardia, arrhythmias, hypertension, often accompanied by systemic hypoperfusion may come [15]. This determines the characteristics of premedication, which should optimally include only benzodiazepines in doses that provide deeper than conventional doses, but well-managed and controlled sedation. Midazolam, a short-acting benzodiazepine, is widely used to address this problem [25]. It is characterized by rapid development of the effect, the absence of local changes and the compatibility with other intravenous drugs used in anesthesiology. The half-life of midazolam is 10 times shorter than that of diazepam and is 2.5-3.5 hours. These properties of the drug allow it to be used in doses that provide deep sedation with a lower risk of postoperative depression. Typically, for premedication, midazolam is administered intramuscularly at a dose of 0.05–0.1 mg / kg 20-30 minutes before anesthesia. Supplemental administration of antihistamines does not improve the quality of premedication, and regular administration of atropine increases the risk of tachycardia and hyperthermia due to blockage of sweat gland secretion. Midazolam may be given intravenously for premedication (0.05-0.1 mg / kg) in emotionally labile patients who do not have existing and potential thyrotoxicosis compensation in the preoperative period.

At present, most thyroid surgeries are performed under general anesthesia with tracheal intubation and artificial respiration, which has almost completely replaced other methods of pain relief. Under general anesthesia with general intravenous or inhalation anesthetics, trachea shifts, deforms and compresses, the presence of endotracheal tubes in the airways in the case of forced hospitalization, the use of free and adequate ventilation during surgery [14, 15]. and provides a controlled depth and an estimated duration of anesthesia [28, 29].

In patients with toxic and non-toxic anesthesia, access anesthesia is performed by combining barbiturates, fentanyl, and muscle relaxants. One of the advantages of using barbiturates for induction anesthesia is their ability to affect the level of thyroid hormones in the blood, as they have a blocking effect on the function of the thyroid gland [15, 16]. Propofol is also currently used for induction anesthesia. Propofol significantly reduces the overall resistance of peripheral blood vessels, myocardial contractility and preload, which can lead to a significant decrease in blood pressure. Arterial hypotension is complicated by the use of large doses of propofol, overdose, and aging of the patient [26]. A small amount of narcotic analgesics (fentanyl) is added to the anesthetic induction to best protect against pathological reflexes that occur in response to tracheal intubation.

Difficulties in tracheal intubation are associated with impaired topographic and anatomical integrity of the neck in 15-18% of patients with thyroid disease, as well as short and thick necks in some patients, increased sensitivity of the mucous membranes to mechanical injury [16]. Intubation, which is difficult to perform in thyroid surgery, is exacerbated by the inability to use a number of alternative methods, such as enlarged thyroid gland, retrograde intubation, transtracheal oxygen breathing, and transtracheal reactive ventilation. According to the ASA (ASA) guidelines, “difficult intubation” is a clinical condition in which the anesthesiologist has difficulty in masked ventilation and tracheal intubation. Intubation is considered difficult when the anesthesiologist requires more than three attempts at standard laryngoscopy or more than 10 minutes to achieve the correct position of the endotracheal tube [30]. An important decision when difficult intubation occurs is to choose movement through “forward” or “backward” strategies. The “forward movement” strategy involves deepening muscle relaxation to improve anesthesia and laryngoscopy. This strategy has not been shown in patients with thyrotoxicosis due to increased oxygen demand and a sharp increase in carbon dioxide sensitivity in these patients [16]. In endocrine surgery, a "backward movement" strategy is

preferred, that is, to stop anesthesia and restore independent breathing. This solution allows you to find the best way to ensure airway patency using a variety of methods [31]. One of the most promising methods is mask induction with sevoflurane, which is performed to ensure that the patient breathes independently and is well controlled in depth and duration. Induction using sevoflurane is repeated at any stage of anesthesia induction [32]. Also, one of the alternative methods is nasotracheal intubation in the form of independent breathing [15]. If unsuccessful, they resort to tracheal intubation using a fibrobronchoscope. In modern conditions, fibroscopic intubation is considered the “gold standard” when technical difficulties arise [33]. Recently, an laryngeal mask has been used as an alternative to tracheal intubation. However, compared to other endotracheal tubes, this method has a number of obvious advantages in the case of laryngeal masking - rapid installation without the use of a laryngoscope, less traumatic installation, no risk of intubation of the esophagus and main bronchus.

In addition, the laryngeal mask, due to its wider permeability and less resistance to breathing, also helps in the early recovery of cough. The minimal effect of the laryngeal mask on oropharyngeal, throat and tracheal receptors allows patients to breathe spontaneously very easily and safely, in some cases combining this treatment with auxiliary mechanical ventilation [34].

Discussion:

In thyroid surgery, the body must have a certain level of anesthetic protection [35, 36]. The choice of anesthesia should take into account many factors, such as its effect on the cardiovascular system, the secretion of thyroid hormones, the parenchymal organs and the functional state of the thyroid gland [15]. Until recently, inhaled anesthetics such as ether, cyclopropane, galotan, methoxyflurane, or neuroleptanalgesia were widely used in diffuse toxic bowel operations. These drugs almost do not change the content of thyroid-stimulating hormone in the plasma of a patient with thyrotoxicosis [37]. When using ether, the amount of thyroxine in the blood plasma increases by 25%, in galotan - by 12%. Methoxyflurane has no significant effect on blood T4 levels, and thiopental sodium and local anesthetics significantly reduce it. All inhaled anesthetics, including morphine, diazepam, ketamine, local anesthetics, and neuroleptanalgesia, reduce plasma T3 by an average of 30% [15]. Halothane moderately reduces thyroid function and, in combination with neuroleptanalgesia, provides good control of anesthesia and adequate neurovegetative protection [16, 21]. Isoflurane has minimal organ toxicity [38 - 40]. The use of isoflurane has a positive effect on blood flow to the organs due to its direct vasodilating effect [41].

Isoflurane anesthesia is characterized by a very short duration of action and a sufficient therapeutic breadth, providing more stable hemodynamic parameters and faster awakening compared to galotanic anesthesia [42-44]. However, all of these inhalation anesthetics are not without their drawbacks. Halothane reduces systemic blood flow, has a cardiodepressant effect, makes the myocardium sensitive to catecholamines, and is toxic to the liver [45, 46]; nephrotoxic methoxyflurane; enflurane - can stimulate the thyroid gland; isoflurane - significantly reduces blood pressure and systemic vascular resistance, especially in dehydrated patients and patients with low myocardial reserve [26, 47]. For these reasons, third-generation inhalation anesthetics such as sevoflurane and xenon are now increasingly used in clinical practice [26, 48, 49]. Sevofluran, as well as isoflurane, have been shown to be minimally toxic to the body [38 - 40, 50] and to have a wide range of therapeutic effects for anesthesia and recovery [43], 44, 51]. Sevoflurane has less effect on hemodynamics than isoflurane and desflurane [49] and has a more significant cardioprotective effect than intravenous anesthesia [52]. Sevoflurane does not affect myocardial sensitivity to adrenaline when arrhythmias are observed in more than 60% of patients under inhalation anesthesia with galotan and enflurane [53].

Xenon, previously an inert gas in European countries and in Russia since 1999, has been registered for medical purposes and is actively used for anesthesia; It has been more than 50 years since it was first used as an anesthetic [55, 56]. The use of xenon is of particular interest in modern and convenient anesthesiology. Undoubtedly, this is supported by many fundamental studies, experiments, and pre-clinical trials that have provided a theoretical and methodological basis for the use of xenon in clinical practice, as well as the development of special dosimeters and gas analyzers [57 - 60]. Xenon is not toxic to the patient [57, 61] and is not contraindicated in patients with severe

endotoxicosis of various etiologies [62]. When studying the effect of xenon on thyroid function, an increase in TS levels was observed in the context of physiological oscillations, and a decrease in T3 and T4 hormone levels was observed in the normal range. According to the dynamics of thyroid hormones, it can be said that xenon anesthesia corresponds to the nature of surgical intervention [36].

Medical gas xenon increases stable hemodynamics, moderate vasoplegia, increased blood flow to the organs, improved microcirculation and the volume of the cardiovascular system [57, 63, 64]. Clinical studies have shown that the use of medical gas xenon does not significantly affect central hemodynamics [65, 66], and that xenon at 60-65% does not alter AHB in patients with severe heart failure.

Conclusions:

In recent decades, the trend to expand the scope of surgical treatment of patients with thyroid disease [68] is not only due to the improved surgical techniques of surgeons, but also to the fact that anesthesiologists provide a safe operation period with a wide range of techniques. It should be noted that the success of surgical treatment of toxic and non-toxic bulls depends on the selection and provision of an effective method of anesthesia in surgical intervention. Patients operated on for thyroid diseases, in the intraoperative period, undesirable hemodynamic, vegetative and neuroendocrine reactions of the body occur, which negatively affect the course of the perioperative period and the anesthetic allowance.

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